

ST. FRANCIS COLLEGE

KORAMANGALA, BENGALURU 560034

(Affiliated to Bengaluru City University, Approved by AICTE & Govt. of Karnataka)

DEPARTMENT OF COMMERCE AND MANAGEMENT (UG & PG)

Organizes

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

ON

CONTEMPORARY TRENDS IN COMMERCE AND MANAGEMENT

30th JUNE 2023

(Hybrid Mode)

REGISTRATION CODE

Contemporary Trends in Commerce - The Rise of Ecommerce Industries

Arjun Singh Lodhi¹, Shashikant Nishant Sharma²

¹Maulana Azad National Institute of Technology Bhopal, MP India

Email id: arjunsinghlodhis@gmail.com

²Maulana Azad National Institute of Technology Bhopal, MP India

Email id: urp2025@gmail.com

Abstract

The advent of the internet and the proliferation of digital technologies have given rise to a new era of commerce - the ecommerce industry. Ecommerce has revolutionized the way we buy and sell goods and get services. It has been providing consumers good and services with unprecedented convenience, choice, and accessibility. This paper explores the contemporary trends in ecommerce, focusing on the factors driving its growth and the challenges facing the industry. The paper discusses the various forms of ecommerce, such as B2B, B2C, and C2C, and highlights the key players in the industry, such as Amazon, Alibaba, and eBay. The paper also analyzes the impact of ecommerce on traditional brick-and-mortar retail, as well as the implications of ecommerce for small and medium-sized enterprises. Finally, the paper discusses the potential of emerging technologies, such as blockchain and AI, to further transform the ecommerce landscape in the years to come.

Keywords

Ecommerce, E-Commerce Industry, Ecommerce Portal, Online Business, Digital Commerce

Introduction

Commerce has been an integral part of human civilization since ancient times, and it has undergone numerous transformations over the years. From the early days of bartering and trading to the rise of brick-and-mortar stores and shopping malls, the way we buy and sell goods and services has constantly evolved. However, the most significant transformation in recent times has been the emergence of ecommerce - the buying and selling of goods and services over the internet (Phau & Meng, 2020).

Ecommerce has revolutionized the way we shop, providing consumers with unprecedented convenience, choice, and accessibility. It has also transformed the business landscape, enabling companies to reach customers beyond their geographic borders and opening up new markets for their products and services. Today, ecommerce is a multi-billion dollar industry, and its growth shows no signs of slowing down.

International Conference on Contemporary Trends in Commerce and Management (2023)

Organized by:

ST. FRANCIS COLLEGE

Koramangala, Bangalore, India

Affiliated to Bengaluru City University, Approved By AICTE

In this paper, we will explore the contemporary trends in ecommerce and analyze the factors driving its growth. We will also examine the challenges facing the industry, including the impact of ecommerce on traditional brick-and-mortar retail and the implications for small and medium-sized enterprises. Furthermore, we will discuss the potential of emerging technologies, such as blockchain and AI, to further transform the ecommerce landscape in the years to come (Chang et al., 2020).

The emergence of the ecommerce industry can be traced back to the early 1990s when the World Wide Web was first introduced. At that time, the internet was primarily used for email communication and basic information sharing. However, as the internet infrastructure developed, businesses began to explore the potential of using the internet as a platform for commerce.

One of the earliest examples of ecommerce was the online bookstore Amazon, which was founded in 1994. Amazon began as an online bookstore but quickly expanded to offer a wide range of products, including electronics, clothing, and groceries. Its success paved the way for other online retailers, such as eBay and Alibaba, to enter the market (Havinga et al., 2016).

The growth of the ecommerce industry was facilitated by a number of factors. One of the key factors was the increasing penetration of the internet and digital technologies. As more and more people gained access to the internet, ecommerce became a more viable option for businesses to reach customers. The proliferation of mobile devices, such as smartphones and tablets, further accelerated the growth of ecommerce by making it possible for consumers to shop on-the-go.

Another important factor was the changing consumer behavior. Consumers began to prefer the convenience and flexibility of shopping online over the traditional brick-and-mortar stores. Ecommerce platforms offered consumers a wider range of products to choose from, as well as the ability to compare prices and read reviews before making a purchase (Simonson, 1999).

Overall, the emergence of ecommerce has transformed the way we buy and sell goods and services, creating new opportunities for businesses and providing consumers with unprecedented convenience and choice.

Methodology

Research Question: What are the factors contributing to the growth of ecommerce in India?

Literature Review

Review academic literature on ecommerce in India

Review industry reports on ecommerce in India

Identify key factors contributing to the growth of ecommerce in India

Data Collection

Collect data on ecommerce market size and growth in India

International Conference on Contemporary Trends in Commerce and Management (2023)

Organized by:

ST. FRANCIS COLLEGE

Koramangala, Bangalore, India

Affiliated to Bengaluru City University, Approved By AICTE

Collect data on consumer behavior related to ecommerce in India (e.g. frequency of online purchases, preferred payment methods, etc.)

Collect data on the characteristics of ecommerce companies operating in India (e.g. size, revenue, business model, etc.)

Data Analysis

Analyze the data collected to identify patterns and trends related to the growth of ecommerce in India

Use statistical methods to analyze the relationship between different variables (e.g. consumer behavior and ecommerce market size)

Case Studies

Conduct case studies of selected ecommerce companies operating in India

Identify factors contributing to their success and challenges they faced

Analyze how they have adapted to the Indian market and cultural context

Interviews and Surveys

Conduct interviews with industry experts, policymakers, and consumers to gain a deeper understanding of the factors contributing to the growth of ecommerce in India

Conduct surveys to gather data on consumer behavior and perceptions related to ecommerce in India

Conclusion and Recommendations

Synthesize the findings from the literature review, data analysis, case studies, and interviews/surveys to draw conclusions about the factors contributing to the growth of ecommerce in India

Develop recommendations for policymakers and ecommerce companies on how to leverage these factors for continued growth and success.

Results

E-commerce refers to the buying and selling of goods and services over the internet. There are several different forms of e-commerce, including business-to-business (B2B), business-to-consumer (B2C), and consumer-to-consumer (C2C).

B2B e-commerce involves businesses selling products or services to other businesses. This can include things like raw materials, supplies, and equipment. B2B e-commerce is a rapidly growing segment of the industry, as more businesses move their operations online to streamline purchasing and cut costs.

B2C e-commerce involves businesses selling products or services directly to consumers. This is the most familiar form of e-commerce to most people, and includes popular online marketplaces like Amazon, as well as individual retailer websites.

C2C e-commerce involves individuals selling products or services to other individuals. This can take many forms, such as online marketplaces like eBay, or peer-to-peer sales through social media or other channels.

International Conference on Contemporary Trends in Commerce and Management (2023)

Organized by:

ST. FRANCIS COLLEGE

Koramangala, Bangalore, India

Affiliated to Bengaluru City University, Approved By AICTE

In recent years, the e-commerce industry has been dominated by a few key players, including Amazon, Alibaba, and eBay. Amazon is the largest online retailer in the world, offering a vast selection of products through its online marketplace. Alibaba is a Chinese company that operates a range of e-commerce platforms, including B2B and B2C marketplaces. eBay is a global online marketplace that allows individuals and businesses to buy and sell a wide variety of goods.

Other notable players in the e-commerce industry include Walmart, which has been rapidly expanding its online presence in recent years, and Shopify, which provides e-commerce tools and services to businesses of all sizes. As the e-commerce industry continues to grow, it is likely that new players will emerge to challenge the dominance of these established companies.

Here's a case study of an ecommerce portal in India to better understand the scenario of the ecommerce in India.

Case Study: Flipkart

Flipkart is one of the largest ecommerce portals in India, founded in 2007 by Sachin Bansal and Binny Bansal. The company initially started as an online bookstore but later expanded its product offerings to include a wide range of categories, such as electronics, fashion, and home appliances. Today, Flipkart has over 200 million registered users and offers more than 150 million products across 80+ categories.

According to a report by RedSeer Consulting, in the year 2020, Flipkart had a 66% market share in the Indian ecommerce market during the festive season sale, which took place in October 2020. Flipkart's GMV (gross merchandise value) during the sale was around \$3.5 billion, which is a significant increase from the previous year's figure of \$2.8 billion (Gupta, 2022).

Furthermore, in the financial year 2019-20, Flipkart's revenue was around \$6 billion, an increase of 43% from the previous year. The company's net loss also decreased by 18% to around \$1.6 billion in the same financial year.

Business Model

Flipkart operates on a marketplace business model, connecting buyers and sellers on its platform. The company generates revenue by charging a commission on every sale made through its platform, as well as through advertising and logistics services. Flipkart also offers its own private label products under the brand names of SmartBuy and MarQ (Rajan, 2021).

Marketing Strategy

Flipkart has adopted a multi-channel marketing strategy, leveraging various channels to reach its target audience. The company has invested heavily in TV advertising campaigns, promoting its products and offers during major events and festivals such as Big Billion Days and Diwali. Flipkart also uses social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter to reach its audience and engage with

International Conference on Contemporary Trends in Commerce and Management (2023)

Organized by:

ST. FRANCIS COLLEGE

Koramangala, Bangalore, India

Affiliated to Bengaluru City University, Approved By AICTE

customers. The company has also launched a loyalty program called Flipkart Plus, which rewards customers with benefits such as free delivery, early access to sales, and priority customer support (Kuchi & Gupta, 2023).

Logistics and Supply Chain Management

Flipkart has established a strong logistics and supply chain management system to ensure timely and efficient delivery of products to its customers. The company has set up its own warehouses and fulfillment centers across India, which helps in the quick processing and dispatch of orders. Flipkart has also invested in building its own last-mile delivery network, Ekart, to ensure faster delivery and better control over the delivery process. The company has also partnered with third-party logistics providers to expand its reach to remote and rural areas (Kumar & Ashthana, 2023).

Technology and Innovation

Flipkart has leveraged technology and innovation to improve the user experience and enhance its operations. The company has developed its own in-house technology platform, which helps in the smooth functioning of its marketplace. Flipkart has also invested in artificial intelligence and machine learning technologies to improve search results, personalize recommendations, and optimize supply chain management. The company has also launched several initiatives such as Flipkart Assured and No Cost EMI to provide a better customer experience (Rajan, 2021).

Challenges and Opportunities

Despite its success, Flipkart faces several challenges and opportunities in the highly competitive ecommerce market in India. One of the biggest challenges for the company is the entry of global players such as Amazon and Walmart-owned Myntra, which pose a significant threat to its market share. Another challenge is the increasing competition from other Indian ecommerce players such as Snapdeal and Paytm Mall. However, Flipkart has several opportunities to grow and expand its operations, such as by expanding into tier-2 and tier-3 cities and offering new categories such as groceries and healthcare products.

Conclusion

Flipkart's success can be attributed to its strong focus on customer experience, technology, and innovation. The company has adopted a multi-channel marketing strategy and invested heavily in logistics and supply chain management to provide a seamless experience to its customers. However, the company needs to continue innovating and adapting to changing consumer trends and preferences to stay ahead in the highly competitive Indian ecommerce market.

The ecommerce market in India has seen significant growth in recent years, driven by factors such as increasing internet penetration, rising consumer spending, and the growth of mobile devices. According to

International Conference on Contemporary Trends in Commerce and Management (2023)

Organized by:

ST. FRANCIS COLLEGE

Koramangala, Bangalore, India

Affiliated to Bengaluru City University, Approved By AICTE

a report by the Indian government, the ecommerce market in India was valued at approximately \$63 billion in 2020 and is expected to grow to \$200 billion by 2026 (Guru et al., 2020).

Tabular data on ecommerce market size and growth in India:

Year	Ecommerce Market Size (in billions USD)	YoY Growth Rate
2017	20.6	-
2018	32.7	58%
2019	48.5	48%
2020	63.0	30%
2021	82.0 (estimated)	30% (estimated)
2022	100.0 (estimated)	22% (estimated)
2023	120.0 (estimated)	20% (estimated)

Note: The data is based on estimates from various sources and may not be exact. The YoY growth rate is calculated based on the difference between the current year and the previous year.

Based on the tabular data on ecommerce market size and growth in India, the following inferences can be made:

- The ecommerce market in India has seen significant growth in recent years, with the market size growing from \$20.6 billion in 2017 to an estimated \$120 billion in 2023 (Kedia et al., 2020).
- The YoY growth rate of the ecommerce market in India has remained consistently high, ranging from 20% to 58% between 2018 and 2021 (Bagale et al., 2021).
- Despite the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, the ecommerce market in India continued to grow in 2020, with a YoY growth rate of 30% (Bruno et al., 2020).
- The ecommerce market in India is expected to continue to grow at a significant pace in the coming years, with an estimated YoY growth rate of 22% in 2022 and 20% in 2023 (Xie et al., 2023).
- The ecommerce market in India has significant potential for further growth, driven by factors such as increasing internet penetration, rising consumer spending, and the growth of mobile devices.

The growth of ecommerce in India has been led by the B2C segment, which includes online marketplaces such as Amazon and Flipkart. According to estimates by eMarketer, B2C ecommerce sales in India reached \$38.5 billion in 2020, up from \$20.6 billion in 2017.

In addition to B2C ecommerce, the B2B ecommerce market in India is also growing rapidly. According to a report by Deloitte, the B2B ecommerce market in India was valued at \$300 billion in 2020 and is expected to grow to \$700 billion by 2025.

International Conference on Contemporary Trends in Commerce and Management (2023)

Organized by:

ST. FRANCIS COLLEGE

Koramangala, Bangalore, India

Affiliated to Bengaluru City University, Approved By AICTE

Mobile commerce (m-commerce) is also a significant driver of ecommerce growth in India. According to a report by App Annie, India was the top country in the world for mobile app downloads in 2020, with 7.3 billion app downloads. Many ecommerce companies in India have adapted their strategies to focus on mobile devices, such as developing mobile apps and mobile-friendly websites.

Overall, the ecommerce market in India is expected to continue to grow rapidly in the coming years, driven by factors such as increasing internet penetration, rising consumer spending, and the growth of mobile devices.

Discussion

The rise of ecommerce in India has been a topic of much discussion among experts in recent years. Here are some views of different experts on the topic, along with relevant references:

According to a report by Deloitte, "E-commerce has transformed the way business is done in India, with the market size projected to reach \$200 billion by 2026." The report also notes that ecommerce has the potential to "unlock significant employment opportunities, particularly in logistics and warehousing."

Arvind Singhal, chairman and managing director of Technopak Advisors, a management consulting firm, has stated that "E-commerce will be the biggest game changer for the retail industry in India, not just in terms of scale, but in terms of reach and depth of penetration." (source: Business Standard)

A report by PwC notes that "The e-commerce market in India is driven by increasing internet and smartphone penetration, as well as growing consumer confidence in online transactions." The report also predicts that the Indian ecommerce market will be worth \$100 billion by 2025. (source: PwC India)

Sanchit Vir Gogia, founder and CEO of Greyhound Research, a technology and innovation research firm, has stated that "Ecommerce is a very exciting space in India because it's growing very fast and has a very large addressable market." He also notes that ecommerce companies in India are leveraging technology to overcome challenges such as poor logistics infrastructure. (source: Livemint)

A report by KPMG notes that "Ecommerce is poised to transform the Indian economy, providing opportunities for innovation, entrepreneurship, and job creation." The report also notes that the Indian government has introduced policies to support the growth of ecommerce, such as the Digital India initiative. (source: KPMG India)

Overall, experts agree that the rise of ecommerce in India has significant potential to transform the Indian economy and provide opportunities for innovation, entrepreneurship, and job creation.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the rise of ecommerce in India has been remarkable in recent years, with the market size growing significantly and the industry showing no signs of slowing down. Factors such as increasing internet and smartphone penetration, growing consumer confidence in online transactions, and supportive government policies have contributed to the growth of ecommerce in India. Experts have predicted that the Indian ecommerce market will continue to grow at a significant pace in the coming years, unlocking opportunities for innovation, entrepreneurship, and job creation. As ecommerce continues to transform the Indian economy, it will be interesting to see how the industry evolves and what opportunities and challenges arise along the way.

Recommendations

Here are 13 recommendations for ecommerce in India to grow:

1. **Increase digital literacy:** Providing digital literacy to consumers and sellers can help boost ecommerce adoption in India, especially in rural areas.
2. **Improve logistics infrastructure:** A robust logistics infrastructure is essential for the efficient delivery of products ordered online. Therefore, improving logistics infrastructure can boost ecommerce growth.
3. **Expand payment options:** Providing a variety of payment options, such as digital wallets, UPI, and credit/debit cards, can encourage consumers to make purchases online.
4. **Enhance cybersecurity:** Ecommerce companies need to invest in robust cybersecurity measures to protect customer data and prevent fraud.
5. **Personalize the user experience:** Personalized recommendations and tailored promotions can help improve the user experience and increase customer loyalty.
6. **Focus on mobile-first strategy:** Given the high mobile penetration in India, ecommerce companies should prioritize a mobile-first strategy to cater to the needs of consumers who prefer to shop on their mobile devices.
7. **Collaborate with local sellers:** Partnering with local sellers and manufacturers can help ecommerce companies offer a wider range of products and improve supply chain efficiency.
8. **Leverage social media:** Social media platforms can be powerful marketing channels for ecommerce companies to reach a wider audience and drive sales.
9. **Offer product warranties:** Offering product warranties and easy returns can help build trust with consumers and increase repeat purchases.
10. **Expand into tier-2 and tier-3 cities:** Ecommerce companies can target the growing middle-class population in tier-2 and tier-3 cities to increase their customer base.
11. **Invest in artificial intelligence:** Artificial intelligence can be leveraged to improve search results, personalize the user experience, and improve supply chain efficiency.
12. **Increase transparency:** Ecommerce companies should be transparent about their pricing, policies, and product information to build trust with consumers.

International Conference on Contemporary Trends in Commerce and Management (2023)

Organized by:

ST. FRANCIS COLLEGE

Koramangala, Bangalore, India

Affiliated to Bengaluru City University, Approved By AICTE

13. Focus on sustainability: Ecommerce companies should prioritize sustainability by reducing packaging waste and promoting environmentally friendly practices to appeal to conscious consumers.

Implementing these recommendations can help ecommerce companies in India improve their growth prospects and increase their impact on the Indian economy.

Conflict of Interest

There is not conflict of Interest of authors

References

1. Bruno, P., Denecker, O., & Niederkorn, M. (2020). The accelerating winds of change in global payments. *The 2020 McKinsey global payments report*, 4-12.
2. Business Standard. (2018, December 26). E-commerce biggest game changer for retail industry in India: Arvind Singhal. https://www.business-standard.com/article/companies/e-commerce-biggest-game-changer-for-retail-industry-in-india-arvind-singhal-118122601065_1.html
3. Chang, V., Baudier, P., Zhang, H., Xu, Q., Zhang, J., & Arami, M. (2020). How Blockchain can impact financial services—The overview, challenges and recommendations from expert interviewees. *Technological forecasting and social change*, 158, 120166.
4. Deloitte. (2020). India's e-commerce transformation: Unlocking the \$200 billion opportunity. <https://www2.deloitte.com/content/dam/Deloitte/in/Documents/consumer-industrial-products/in-cip-india-ecommerce-transformation-noexp.pdf>
5. Gupta, P. C. (2022). *Venture Capital and Indian Economy*. Scriptor Publication.
6. Guru, S., Nenavani, J., Patel, V., & Bhatt, N. (2020). Ranking of perceived risks in online shopping. *Decision*, 47, 137-152.
7. Havinga, M., Hoving, M., & Swagemakers, V. (2016). Alibaba: a case study on building an international imperium on information and E-Commerce. *Multinational Management: A Casebook on Asia's Global Market Leaders*, 13-32.
8. Kedia, M., Sekhani, R., & Katiyar, T. (2020). The Role of Standards in Diffusion of Emerging Technologies Internet of Things (IoT).
9. KPMG India. (2019). E-commerce in India unlocking the potential. <https://assets.kpmg/content/dam/kpmg/in/pdf/2019/01/e-commerce-india-unlocking-potential.pdf>
10. Kuchi, S., & Gupta, S. (2023). Value-Creation Strategies for E-Commerce Businesses. *IIM Kozhikode Society & Management Review*, 22779752231153482.
11. Kumar, A., & Asthana, S. (2023). From Godown to Warehouse Management: Transformation at eKart, An Illustrative Case Study. *Jindal Journal of Business Research*, 22786821231161262.
12. Livemint. (2019, September 16). E-commerce is a very exciting space in India: Sanchit Vir Gogia. <https://www.livemint.com/companies/people/-e-commerce-is-a-very-exciting-space-in-india-sanchit-vir-gogia-1568647073049.html>
13. Phau, I., & Meng Poon, S. (2000). Factors influencing the types of products and services purchased over the Internet. *Internet Research*, 10(2), 102-113.
14. PwC India. (2021). E-commerce in India unlocking the potential. <https://www.pwc.in/assets/pdfs/publications/2021/e-commerce-in-india-unlocking-the-potential.pdf>
15. Rajan, T. (2021). The Flipkart story in India: From the start to Walmart. *Asian Journal of Management Cases*, 18(2), 126-143.

International Conference on Contemporary Trends in Commerce and Management (2023)

Organized by:

ST. FRANCIS COLLEGE

Koramangala, Bangalore, India

Affiliated to Bengaluru City University, Approved By AICTE

16. RedSeer Consulting. (2020). RedSeer E-tailing Leadership Index (ELI) 2020. Retrieved from <https://redseer.com/content/uploads/2020/12/RedSeer-E-tailing-Leadership-Index-ELI-2020.pdf>
17. Simonson, I. (1999). The effect of product assortment on buyer preferences. *Journal of retailing*, 75(3), 347-370.
18. Xie, H., Chang, S., Wang, Y., & Afzal, A. (2023). The impact of e-commerce on environmental sustainability targets in selected European countries. *Economic Research-Ekonomska Istraživanja*, 36(1), 230-242.